

Code Switching and Code Mixing Used in Maudy Ayunda's YouTube Videos

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ABSTRACT: This final report aimed to identify the types of code-switching and code-mixing. This report analyses Maudy Ayunda's utterances in her YouTube videos, which contained instances of code-switching and code mixing, using the audio as the primary data source. The process involved watching and downloading YouTube videos, listening to the speech, transcribing the utterances into a script for data collection, and then analyzing the data using a descriptive qualitative method. The findings indicated three types of code-switching and code-mixing. The code-switching types included tag-switching (5 data), intra-sentential switching (57 data), and inter-sentential switching (20 data). For code-mixing, the types identified were insertion (56 data), alternation (3 data), and congruent lexicalization (5 data). The writers hope this report will provide valuable insights and expand knowledge on bilingualism, code-switching, and code-mixing.

Keywords: *Code Switching, Code Mixing, Bilingualism*

INTRODUCTION

In today's digital era, the use of multiple languages in various forms of media has become increasingly common. The use of languages that mixed is an unavoidable reality that occurs in Indonesian society with diverse ethnic and cultural backgrounds. Language is the main communication tool and always occurs in a social context (Kuiper & Allan, 2017). Language is a communication tool used between communities in the form of sound symbols produced by the human speech apparatus using vocal symbols or any speech sounds (Owen in Solehan (2011). To communicate widely, adults tend to increase their ability in other languages.

Apart from being a communication tool, language also reflects the identity, culture and social structure of a society. In society, it is important to use appropriate language. This ensures that the message being communicated is understood by listeners or members of the community without any misunderstandings. The study of the functional characteristics of language use and the characteristics of language use is called Sociolinguistics (Ayu & Hadiwijaya, 2024).

Communication patterns in the current era tend to use more than one language, and these are commonly used. Those who can speak more than one language are called bilingual. In Indonesia, bilingualism is a case experienced by almost half of Indonesians. On average, Indonesian people master their regional languages and Indonesian, especially speech varieties. Apart from being bilingual, those who can speak more than two languages are called multilingual.

In bilingualism and multilingualism, mixing or switching of languages can occur. This has led to the phenomenon of code-switching and code mixing which has now become a speaking trend among society, and this style is studied in sociolinguistics. Another interpretation of code-mixing is the use of other elements or language dependencies when using certain languages in speech (Alimin & Eti, 2021). This event occurs when speakers use a certain language, but there are also fragments of other languages in it. This affects several programs in digital media, especially on the YouTube platform, content creators often use code-switching and code-mixing as strategic communication tools. Maudy Ayunda is a content creator who uses code switching and code mixing a lot. Maudy Ayunda's contents on her personal YouTube contain motivation, daily life, experiences and education so that viewers can take away positive messages from every content that is broadcast. Maudy Ayunda is an Indonesian actress, model, activist, writer, content creator and singer-songwriter. Apart from that, she studied at Oxford University, England and continued her Masters at Stanford University. Therefore, the writers choose Maudy Ayunda as the research subject in this report.

Through her videos, Maudy Ayunda smoothly combines Indonesian and English, reflecting the linguistic flexibility inherent in contemporary Indonesian society. This linguistic diversity reflects the trends of multiculturalism and globalization that shape modern communication practices, underscoring the importance of understanding code-switching and code-mixing in the context of digital media. Code-switching and code-mixing allow Maudy

Ayunda to convey subtle meanings, evoke certain emotions, and create stylistic variations, thereby enriching the communicative experience for the audience. Apart from its communicative function, code-switching and code-mixing in Maudy Ayunda's YouTube content also reflect broader socio-cultural dynamics and power structures. Language choice and frequency of switching may be influenced by factors of social identity, status, and the desire to fit into a particular cultural or social group.

In this research, the writers chose to research to find out the types and differences between code-switching and code-mixing. Research on code switching and code mixing, especially on famous Indonesian celebrities who can speak at least two languages, has been carried out by several researchers. One of them is Gultom (2021) with the title "Code Switching and Code Mixing Used by Boy William Video YouTube Channel".

METHOD

This study employed descriptive qualitative research methods. This was a technique used by researchers to uncover knowledge or theories about the study at a specific moment (Mukhtar, 2013). This study employed descriptive qualitative research methods because it derived its data from real-life spoken language, which was subsequently subjected to objective analysis and interpretation. The findings were then articulated in written form, focusing on the phenomenon of code-switching and code-mixing observed in Maudy Ayunda's YouTube videos.

Qualitative research was a methodology that generated descriptive data through written or spoken words, reflecting people's experiences and observable behaviours (Moleong, 2000). The analysis of the phenomena observed in the data was conducted based on Poplack's (1980) theory to identify the types of code-switching and Musyken's (2000) theory to identify the types of code-mixing. These theories were applied to analyzing the occurrence of code-switching and code-mixing used by Maudy Ayunda.

The object of the Research

The research object was chosen from three videos published by Maudy Ayunda on her personal YouTube Videos. The writers focused on analyzing three of Maudy Ayunda's contents with the theme Maudy's Thought, entitled "Study Hacks ala Maudy Ayunda" which was published on May 2, 2023, "Thought on Priorities" which was published on May 11, 2023, and "How to Communicate Effectively in the Workplace" which was published on February 2, 2024.

The focus of the Research

There are many experts with different opinions on the types of code-switching and code-mixing. In this study, the research variables are code switching and code mixing. The writers employed Poplack's (1980) theory to classify the type of code-switching and Musyken's (2000) theory to categorize the type of code-mixing. Below are some indicators to help the writers ensure that her data is complete and valid:

Table 1. Operational Matrix of Research Variables: Code Switching

Variable	Indicator	Criteria
Code Switching	Tag-switching	Insert a tag in the utterance (short phrase/word) The tag is in different language Only happen within a sentence Occur within clause
	Intra-sentential switching	Occur within sentence boundary Occur within a word Occur in the beginning of sentence/middle/end of the sentence Occur in a utterance
	Inter-sentential switching	b) Speaker complete a sentence c) Switch a different language into next sentence

Table 2. Operational Matrix of Research Variables: Code Mixing

Variable	Indicator	Criteria
Code Mixing	Insertion	Occur within a word boundary Occur when lexical item from one language are incorporated into another
	Alternation	Occur when two different languages used in a clause between two languages b) Occur within a phrase or a clause
	Congruent lexicalization	a) Occur morphologically and phonologically

Technique of Analyzing the Data

After all the necessary data were collected through all data collection techniques, the data were analyzed step by step. By categorizing data, describing it in units, synthesizing information, organizing it into patterns, selecting relevant elements for study, and making conclusions, the researcher made the data understandable for themselves and others (Sugiono, 2010). In this research, the writers analyzed the data by categorizing the types of code-switching, categorizing the types of code mixing, tabulating the code-switching and code-mixing, and drawing conclusions from the research.

FINDINGS

This study focused on the types of code-switching and code-mixing. In this particular section, the writers gathered data from data of Maudy Ayunda's utterances in her YouTube Videos as a primary source to address two specific issues outlined in the first chapter. The first is finding the types of code-switching based on Poplack's (1980) theory to identify the types of code-switching: tag-switching, intra-sentential switching, and inter-sentential switching and Musyken's (2000) theory to identify the types of code mixing: insertion, alternation, congruent lexicalization. These theories are applied to analyzing the occurrence of code-switching and code-mixing used by Maudy Ayunda.

The Types of Code Switching Used by Maudy Ayunda

To answer the first statement of problems of study, the writers used Poplack's (1980) theory. According to Poplack (1980), there are three types of code-switching. In this research of Maudy Ayunda's utterances on her YouTube Videos, the writers found eighty-seven code-switching. Those code-switching appears through the following types of code-switching:

a) Tag-switching

Tag switching is a phenomenon where speakers use short expressions (tags) from another

language in their speech. This often occurs either at the beginning or end of a speech. In those videos, Maudy Ayunda sometimes combines language tags into her speech. In research on this type of code-switching, five examples of data were identified that reflect the consistent use of tag transitions.

1. Video: Study Hacks ala Maudy Ayunda. There were 2 data found. They were **Hi guys! Hope you all doing well.** (0:06) and **By the way, ada riset juga sih yang mem-backing style ini.** (5:47)
 2. Video: Thought on Priorities. There were 3 data found. They were **Oh my god! Ternyata yang suka mengambil waktu aku banget tuh kalo miksalnya sore-sore mulai agak bosan tiba-tiba aku main sosmed.** (2:17), **To be honest, aku nggak selalu ngelakuin ini setiap hari karena ini melelahkan.** (5:47), and **So that's Eisen-matrix-Howers for you, What?!?!** (6:11)
- b) Intra-sentential switching

Intra-sentential switching refers to the type of code-switching that occurs in clauses or sentences, where the sentence in one language is switched into another language in the form of words or phrases. This type of code-switching requires the speaker to be fluent in both languages. Phrases and words that appear in code-switching include nouns, adjectives, verbs and adverbs. In this type of code-switching, there are fifty-six data found as follows:

1. Video: Study Hacks ala Maudy Ayunda
 - 1) **For Maudy's Thought** *kali ini, aku juga mau siap-siap sebenarnya as usual, but kali ini siap-siapnya mudah-mudahan lebih instant karena I have meeting that I running to.* (0:09)
 - 2) *Aku tahu temen-temen diluar sana banyak yang lagi mau ujian, so I thought I just want to share some of my studying hacks sambil aku siap-siap* (0:55)

- 3) **So, aku suka banget menjadikan sample question itu patokan, because they are more true to life and you get a better sense of the type of things that you have look for as you studying because you already know the question that will be asked.** (1:48)
- 4) *Sebelum aku baca-baca lagi, I usually just opened up the practice question try to do them, dan dari situ banyak banget informasi yang aku dapetin.* (2:37)
- 5) *Aku tuh kalo siap-siap gini paling jatuhnya just a little bit powder, little bit of mascara, and maybe just like a nice red lipstick.* (2:51)
- 6) *Jadi, the second step is that diagnose.* (3:29)
- 7) **That's why, the initials diagnoses is super important, karena dari situ kita langsung bisa lebih memfokuskan, dan ga buang-buang waktu, dan kita bisa langsung aja fokus ngerjain.** (4:16)
- 8) *Dulu ya waktu aku sekolah dan aku harus menyeimbangi waktu antara kerja sekolah, terus misalnya besoknya mau ujian, I mean I don't have a lot of time to study sometimes you know, jadinya I'm really always try to find a way to study smarter, instead of studying harder or spending more time dan ini salah satu tips jadi lebih efisien kalo kita hanya memprioritaskan kelemahan-kelemahan kita saat kita belajar.* (4:38)
- 9) **Okay in the middle of mencatok, dan aku biasanya nyatok keluar.** (5:31)
- 10) **The third studying hacks yang ini sebenarnya agak aneh karena this is my very-very own unique studying style.** (5:39)
- 11) *Risetnya bilang bahwa kita itu misalnya lagi belajar satu topik we are more likely to master the topic if we teach it to someone else.* (5:53)
- 12) **It's interesting when I read that research waktu aku at an education school, karena aku langsung mikir oh my god I used to that to myself, that was the hack that I was used to do waktu aku SMA.** (6:16)
- 13) **Jadi hack nya adalah setelah aku membaca sebuah chapter atau sebuah topik, I sometimes call my sister in and force her to listen to me and try to teach her seakan-akan aku tu jadi expert nya.** (6:30)
- 14) **I know it's kinda weird, but I used to even record my own voice dimana aku menjelaskan ke orang siapa pun itu tentang si topik ini.** (7:21)
- 15) **So, misalnya kalo dulu "oh this is how the law of supply and demand works" terus aku ajarin aja diri aku sendiri.** (7:44)

- 16) *Karena aku baru inget juga bahwa, oh my god this is something that I used to do definitely something that I think really helpful.* (8:20)
- 17) *Jadi kalo aku lagi buru-buru aku juga ga terlalu lama-lama sih nyatoknya, just so there's a little bit of volume and a little bit of finesse.* (8:26)
- 18) **This is not the most simple, tapi that's fine.** (9:07)
- 19) **Let me show you, aku jadi nambah tinggi, and there's a little bit of red to match my lips.** (9:12)
2. Video: Thought on Priorities
 - 1) *Kemarin kan libur lebaran, I spent some time with my family, aku ke Bali sama keluarga aku.* (0:07)
 - 2) **So I'm sitting here with my laptop dan aku buka kalender just looking at managing my time for the next week.** (0:21)
 - 3) *Aku juga jadi kepikiran untuk bikin konten Maudy's thoughts in the middle of all this.* (0:32)
 - 4) *Karena temen-temen aku tuh banyak banget yang sering nanya ke aku "how do you manage your time, kak Mod? and what are some of the tools that you use so that you can be productive and you can ensure that everything gets done?"* (0:36)
 - 5) *Jadi memang temanya lagi cocok, aku keinget gitu and I wanted to share with you guys, so I took up my cam and there's a lot to cover. So I'm going to need a little bit of coffee.* (0:50)
 - 6) *Karena yang pertama kali kita harus lakuin adalah we have to get rid of the things and the activities that suck up our time, tapi sebenarnya kurang menunjang atau kurang meng-support goal-goal kita jangka panjangnya gitu.* (2:02)
 - 7) *Aku biasanya jam segini sampai segini tuh nonton TV padahal sebenarnya aku lagi nggak terlalu pengen nonton TV gitu, I just kind of wanted to chill.* (2:35)
 - 8) **Identifying moments yang sucking up your time and wasting your time, terus kita deprioritize dulu, itu penting banget.** (2:43)
 - 9) *Point kedua, and I've actually talked about this in my TikTok before that we have to learn how to prioritize.* (3:24)
 - 10) *Mengatakan bahwa 80% dari hasil yang bisa kita capai itu sebenarnya hanya dicapai atau hanya bisa trace to 20% of what we decide to do, of how we choose to spend our time.* (3:36)

- 11) **Example of things like this is kind of like, oh mungkin kayak cleaning the house or sending something. (4:57)**
- 12) **Then, basically the next step nya adalah either do it now, schedule it, delegate it, or delete it. And this is something that I tried to do. (5:38)**
- 13) *Tapi kayak misalnya masa-masa quarterly atau monthly, I try to do this especially when I feel super super overwhelmed dan to do list aku mulai agak banyak. (5:51)*
- 14) *Biasanya, I force myself to kind of like do a complete revisit and evaluation of all the activities that I want to do. (6:02)*
- 15) **I do on a macro level, but on the micro level, secara time management, aku tuh sebenarnya menghindari multitasking. (6:26)**
- 16) *Kalau melakukan itu tuh menurut aku there's a lot of transition costs when you move from one task to another, karena mindset-nya beda. (7:02)*
- 17) **Another thing adalah it just helps you stay present. (7:42)**
- 18) *Kalau kita benar-bener lagi focus ngerjain satu hal aja, we're more present, we're more focus and yeah, of course will be more effective in getting it done. (7:45)*
3. Video: How to communicate effectively in the workplace
 - 1) **One of the question that I get ask a lot is "kak maudy, punya ga sih tips communication in the workplace" (0:36)**
 - 2) *Gimana sih caranya supaya aku perform, bisa success in the workplace because I have good communication. (0:44)*
 - 3) *Aku akan ngomongin 3 hal yang menurut aku practically very useful, and you guys can give it a try in your respective work settings. (0:51)*
 - 4) *Yang pertama, bisa dibilang dari pengalaman aku sebagai public figure yang mungkin mendapatkan public speaking experiences, this is some wisdom that I can share with you guys. (1:10)*
 - 5) **I've noticed different methods and different ways of showing up work better depending on the culture of the place that you're working in, dan kita juga harus memerhatikan dan belajar dulu kulturnya seperti apa sih. (2:03)**
 - 6) *Tapi ada juga beberapa tempat kerja yang culture nya tu very much like perang gitu pada saat kita lagi meeting, so you really to make sure that you get your voice in. (2:33)*
 - 7) *Jadi kamu misalnya baru pertama kali meeting nih kamu perhatiin dulu, do people like it when people speak up, or butt in, or when people are very opinionated, or is it more*

- of a culture of hyper politeness, and waiting for your turn to speak? Karena menurut aku beda-beda nih gitu. (2:52)
- 8) *Tentunya dengan berjalannya waktu kalau kalian memang sudah punya **privilege** memilih tempat kerja kalian, **you can always align or choose a work space yang culture-nya lebih cocok sama kamu.** (4:09)*
 - 9) *Kalau misalnya aku salah ngomong atau deg-degan di 30 detik pertama, biasanya **the rest of my performance, and the rest of my speech** itu juga jadi agak berantakan. (4:52)*
 - 10) *Jadi, **the 30 seconds is really important to get me to a place of comfort and confidence.** (5:09)*
 - 11) ***Whatever you have to say in the first 30 seconds, memorize it, make it perfect,** dan itu akan menjadi **booster.** (5:59)*
 - 12) *Jadi penting banget untuk latihan **pronunciation, and feel like you are getting there.** (7:35)*
 - 13) ***I really recommend that you guys upgrade to Elsa Pro, biar bisa akses all of the lessons, track your progress dan juga dapetin personalized learning plan.** (8:17)*
 - 14) *Misalnya yang **pronunciation exercise,** kita bisa latihan ngomong Inggris terus Elsa bisa **detect how good our pronunciation is, show our mistake, dan kasih feedback** sedetail ini. (8:35)*
 - 15) ***You can kind of set the setting and,** lucunya ada juga disini latihan ngomong **in the context of online dating.** (9:16)*
 - 16) *Di sini tuh bener-bener dijabarin menurut interaksi tadi kamu tuh kemampuannya udah di mana sekarang, secara **pronunciation, vocabulary, grammar, and it's all like done in quite a lot of detail.** (11:30)*
 - 17) *Seperti yang aku kasih lihat tadi, **if you unlock the premium, you got to even do like a 1-on-1 with Elsa AI.** (11:59)*
 - 18) *Kalian bahkan bisa pake ini untuk latihan **presentasi, job interview, or even prep for your IELTS test with their guided questions.** (12:20)*
 - 19) *Setelah selesai, dia akan kasih **super detailed and scores for us to improve on.** (12:29)*
 - 20) ***I hope that was useful guys, tadi ada 3 tips ya, yang pertama align your communication strategy with the culture of your workplace.** (13:08)*
- c) Inter-sentential switching

Inter-sentential switching occurs in two separate sentences within an utterance. This

can occur when the speaker completes a sentence in one language and then switches to another language in the subsequent sentence. It can also happen when each clause or sentence is exclusively in one language or the other. In this type of code-switching, there are eighteen data found as follow:

1. Video: Study Hacks ala Maudy Ayunda
 - 1) *Aku tu ngerasa a lot of people think that I really-really love exam, and I do like exams. Tapi bukannya aku ngerasa ujian itu seru pada saat ngejalaninnya.* (0:30)
 - 2) *Tapi lebih seru setelahnya. Feeling like I achieve something big and that's quite hard, that sensational feel is what makes it fun.* (0:44)
 - 3) *Okay, tip nomor satu studying hack buat aku adalah practice question. I used to really like practice question* (1:06)
 - 4) *Jadi kita ga buang waktu mempelajari hal hal yang gak perlu dipelajari. We don't have to spend that much time on and so, that take my entire strategy.* (2:12)
 - 5) *I just think that by doing that you can have a look. Terus paling aku nunggu catokan panas, and just gonna ngecatok dikit rambut aku.* (5:19)
 - 6) *I know it's kinda weird, but I used to even record my own voice dimana aku menjelaskan ke orang siapa pun itu tentang si topik ini.* (7:21)
 - 7) *Okay kita cari sepatu dulu, I think let brought super simple.* (8:58)
2. Video: Thought on Priorities
 - 1) **I wanted to talk about the Eisenhower matrix.** *Di matrix ini, kita itu diajarkan untuk mengkategorikan aktivitas kita kepada 4 kategori.* (4:15)
 - 2) *Mungkin aktivitas yang kayak gitu tuh bisa kita delegasikan atau bisa kita bikin jadi kelompok. So we're not the only one doing it.* (5:07)
 - 3) **Believe it or not,** *kopi aku udah hampir abis. It's so nice, so tasty.* (8:22)
 - 4) *Mudah-mudahan kita bisa ngopi-ngopi bareng lagi. Bye! I hope that was helpful guys.* (8:27)
3. Video: How to communicate effectively in the workplace
 - 1) *Jadi sebelum kita membuat asumsi apapun, I think it's really important to observe.* (2:43)
 - 2) **So I call this a kind of like 30 second rule.** *Kenapa sih 30 detik pertamatuh krusial banget?* (4:45)

- 3) *Jadi salah satu tips buat temen-temen yang misalnya harus presentasi, akan didenger banyak orang, akan didengar direksi, itu kan pasti kalian deg-degan banget gitu. **I would suggest, after practicing the entire thing, I would also really, really, really focus on what you have to say in first 30 seconds.** (5:15)*
- 4) *Biasanya kalau misalnya 30 detik pertama aku udah lancar, sisanya aku akan lebih pede. Kalaupun salah, aku jadi ngerasa **it's okey, I can get over it, I did a really good job when I started this talk and I'm gonna smooth it over.** (6:06)*
- 5) *Bahasa tuh medium yang sangat penting untuk berkomunikasi dan juga supaya kita bisa ngerasa **connected** dengan temen-temen bekerja kita. **Language is a really important thing for you can improve on too.** (6:46)*
- 6) *Buat yang baru mulai belajar Bahasa Inggris, **they will adjust to that.** (8:07)*
- 7) ***You basically can choose to practice having conversations in different settings.** Kamu bisa milih misalnya, oh aku mau latihan **interview** kerja nih. (9:00)*
- 8) *Aku mau kasih lihat keseruan pake aplikasi ini, **so you gonna see it here.** (9:32)*
- 9) ***It will help you a lot with getting you that level of confidence.** Kadang-kadang kita sebenarnya udah tau harus ngomong apa, cuma kita takut aja **pronunciation-nya** salah. (13:43)*

The Types of Code Mixing Used by Maudy Ayunda

To answer the second statement of problems of study, the writers used Musyken's (2000) theory. Muysken (2000) proposes three types of code-mixing processes. In this research of Maudy Ayunda's utterances on her YouTube Videos, the writers found eighty-seven code-mixing. Those code-mixing are appeared through the following types of code mixing:

a) Insertion

Insertion relates to the insertion of words or phrases, in other words, the insertion is carried out on syntactic elements, which can be in the form of lexical elements or phrases (Ramadhani, 2011). As Muysken (2000) explains code mixing is understood as a phenomenon similar to word borrowing; where lexical categories or phrases from a foreign language are inserted into the structure of the language being used.

1. Video: Study Hack ala Maudy Ayunda
 - 1) *Tapi topiknya ga kalah seru karena aku pengen ngangkat **studying**.* (0:24)
 - 2) *Cari pertanyaan mungkin dari ujian-ujian lalu atau dari buku-buku **textbook** sekolah, biasanya di bagian-bagian **ending chapter** tu ada kayak **sample question**.* (1:15)
 - 3) *Kenapa sih **sample question** tu penting banget?* (1:30)
 - 4) *Menurut aku apa yang kita pelajarin secara **textbook** dan apa yang akan ditanyakan itu kadang-kadang berbeda **angle*** (1:32)
 - 5) *Kita harus membiasakan diri berpikir dengan **angle** pertanyaan-pertanyaan yang akan keluar di **exam**.* (1:41)
 - 6) *Jadi tip secara **general** aku adalah, gimana caranya kita tuh belajar seefisien mungkin.* (2:06)
 - 7) *Dan kenapa **past question** atau **practice question** itu penting, karena kita tuh langsung memfokuskan diri kita terhadap pertanyaan-pertanyaan yang **actually metter**.* (2:22)
 - 8) *Nah misalnya temen-temen udah latihan **some practice questions**, biasanya dari situ aku akan **grading** diri aku sendiri.* (3:14)
 - 9) ***And then also**, dari diagnosis itu jita tahu jadinya pertanyaan apa aja yang kita tu kurang, yang kita punya **weakness**.* (3:35)
 - 10) *Habiskanlah waktu terbesar untuk mempelajari topik-topik itu aja, jadi topik-topik yang memang kita tuh sering mendapatkan salah, atau kita punya **weakness** gitu, yang bisa kita **diagnose** dari **past test** atau **past sample question** yang kita udah jawab itu.* (3:56)
 - 11) *Akutuh kalo lagi pengen **simple look** justru bibir aku tuh aku pilih warna yang agak **poppy**, karena ga terlalu sempet ngerjain yang lain-lain.* (5:10)
 - 12) *jadi kalo kita belajar dan kita habis itu harus mengajarkan topik atau pelajaran itu ke orang lain akhirnya topik itu jauh lebih nempel juga di kepala kita, **and will be able to master it more naturally** gitu.* (6:05)
 - 13) *Biasanya aku melakukan ini justru di topik-topik yang agak sulit, yang aku pun agak **struggle** untuk mengerti.* (6:43)
 - 14) *Pada saat kita harus **paraphrasing** atau harus menjelaskan kembali ke orang lain yang mungkin tidak memiliki konteks sama sekali, kita tuh jadi terpaksa harus lebih **clear**, lebih **consist**, akhirnya lebih nempel di kepala aku, **I think that's very powerfull**.* (6:48)
 - 15) *Kadang-kadang kalo misalnya adik aku tuh lagi males atau lagi gak mau jadi **my pretend student**, **I talk to myself**.* (7:11)

- 16) *Gak selalu ya, tapi hanya beberapa topik-topik tertentu, terus aku nyalain kayak **voice note and I just talk to myself**. (7:36)*
- 17) *Dulu biologi **I used to that**, karena Biologi tuh banyak banget kayak gambar-gambar grafis gitu, dan ada banyak **memorization** juga karena ada **term-term** tertentu. (7:54)*
- 18) *Ini sebenarnya aku belum pernah **reveal** ke siapa-siapa sih **studying hacks** yang ini. (8:16)*
2. Video: Thought on Priorities
 - 1) *Sekarang hari minggu, **it's the weekend before** aku mulai aktif lagi. (0:14)*
 - 2) *Menurut aku yang pertama banget harus kita lakuin kalua misalnya pengen **reorganize and** pengen **manage your time better** adalah audit dulu. (1:29)*
 - 3) *Jadi meng-audit **schedules** kita selama ini, meng-audit **habits** kita selama ini. (1:39)*
 - 4) *Buka misalnya kalender kamu, atau lihat balik ke **schedules** kamu beberapa minggu yang lalu apa saja yang kamu lakuin? **Habit** kamu tu seperti apa? Bangun jam berapa? dan diantaranya tu ngapain aja? (1:45)*
 - 5) *Jadi meng-audit dulu aja sih, kita harus benar-bener kenal sama diri kita sendiri, sebenarnya kecenderungan-kecenderungan dan **bad habits** kita dalam **time management** itu apa. (2:52)*
 - 6) *Jadi ada satu **principle** namanya Pareto **principle**. (3:32)*
 - 7) *Jadi kebayang gak sih, betapa pentingnya kita tuh benar-bener pinter **prioritizing**. (3:58)*
 - 8) *Karena ternyata apa yang kita lakukan dalam 20% waktu kita aja itu bisa berbuah atau bisa memberi **impact** segitu besarnya dalam hidup kita. (4:03)*
 - 9) *Yang pertama adalah **urgent** dan **important**. (4:28)*
 - 10) *Buat aktivitas yang seperti ini kita harus kerjain sekarang juga, **basically**. (4:30)*
 - 11) *Kategori kedua adalah **Less urgent** tapi itu **important**. Misalnya ya olahraga gitu. Sebenarnya sih gak **urgent** banget tapi ya cukup penting untuk kesehatan kita. (4:38)*
 - 12) *Kita taruh benar-bener di kalender kita, okay sabtu depan **I'm going to do this**. (4:48)*
 - 13) *Kategori ketiga adalah **less important**, jadi ga sepenting itu tapi **urgent**. (4:52)*
 - 14) *Mungkin sifatnya lebih **errands**, atau kayak **grocery shopping**. (5:03)*
 - 15) *Dari situ, kita kategorikan **all that we need to do** ke 4 kategori ini. (5:32)*
 - 16) *Oke, aku yakin disini banyak yang mikir bahwa **I multitask a lot**. (6:19)*
 - 17) *Maksud aku adalah, kalo misalnya kita udah **decide** oke sekarang akan bersih-bersih atau oke sekarang aku akan mengerjakan tugas ini atau menulis esai ini, atau menyelesaikan si*

- meeting notes** ini, atau apapun itu, jangan terus di **multitask** kayak bukak 2 **tabs**, ngerjain **task A sama task B at the same time.** (6:41)
- 18) Jadi kalua kita ngomong **multitasking** secara makro, boleh. (7:13)
 - 19) Itu pasti, **they might** tapi pasti nggak efisien, lompat-lompat terus, dari satu tugas ke tugas lainnya. (8:00)
 - 20) **Thanks for udah nemenin aku di break aku and my coffee time.** (8:12)
 3. Video: How to Communicate Effectively in the Workplace
 - 1) Kali ini lumayan spesial karena akutuh baru sadar juga banyak dari kalian yang ngikutin aku di YouTube atau aku yakin juga di **social platforms** aku yang lainnya itu banyak yang sudah kerja, atau mungkin udah mau lulus jadi lagi **applying**, lagi **first jobber**, atau lagi memulai **internship.** (0:12)
 - 2) Aku pengen kasih **disclaimer** juga bahwa tips-tips ini tuh sebenarnya kombinasi dari banyak hal. (1:05)
 - 3) Aku juga sekarang memiliki **company** sendiri mau itu dibidang media kreatif ataupun di bidang **consumer venture.** (1:23)
 - 4) Karena aku tuh terekspos pada berbagai banyak kultur entah itu **partners** aku atau **companies** gitu yang aku miliki. (1:52)
 - 5) Pokoknya kalau di **meeting** kita harus buru-buru kasih opini, kita harus dominan. (2:19)
 - 6) Gak semua **workplace cultures** itu akan mengapresiasi hal tersebut, mungkin **culture** dia tu lebih **listen first, and then speak.** (2:25)
 - 7) Nah ini sebenarnya aku mendapatkan inspirasi dari **public speaking engagements** aku selama lebih dari 10 tahun di industri media dan hiburan. (4:25)
 - 8) Aku tuh sadar bahwa setiap aku mau **public speaking** atau mau **perform** biasanya aku tuh paling deg-degannya di 30 detik pertama. (4:37)
 - 9) Karena itu yang kalau buat aku sangat **impactful** dalam mempengaruhi **performance** dan juga **confidence** aku selama presentasi yang lainnya. (5:36)
 - 10) “Selamat siang teman-teman, para direksi dan juga **team members**” (5:48)
 - 11) Kalo kita ngomongin bahasa Inggris, kita kan gak cuma ngomongin belajar bahasa inggris secara **formal**, tapi kita juga pengen baget gimana caranya **pronouncation**-nya bisa bagus. (7:11)
 - 12) Kalau kita ngerasa **pronouncation** kita kurang bagus atau cara ngomongnya salah, kita jadi gak berani ngomong juga sih. (7:30)

- 13) **App** ini keren banget karena kalian bisa latihan ngobrol **with their AI technology**. (7:51)
 - 14) Jadi kalau kalian pertama **download**, kalian tuh pasti akan ada **level test** nya dulu. (8:04)
 - 15) Ada banyak interaksi-interaksi **with the AI technology** nya yang membuat kamu tuh ngerasa kayak kamu tuh ngomong sama guru, tapi juga ngomong sama temen. (8:52)
 - 16) Kalau kalian bingung mau jawab apa, sebenarnya Elsa AI nya tu juga kayak ngasih opsi **responses that you can use**. (10:51)
 - 17) Dipaket premiumnya itu udah termasuk Elsa Pro dan **tool** yang namanya **speech analyzes**. (12:13)
 - 18) Untungnya di **app** ini juga bakalan ada **reminder feature**. (12:46)
- b) Alternation

Muysken (2000) explains alternation as the most prevalent code-mixing strategy involves the appearance of two languages in clause form, typically kept separate from each other. If in an utterance contains a mixed clause that begins with language A, then language B is could be used as the following clause. In this type of code-mixing, there are three data as follow:

1. Video: Study Hacks ala Maudy Ayunda
 - 1) Biasanya kalo yang kaya gitu tuh yang paling enak kita pake untuk “mengajarkan” orang lain atau diri kita sendiri karena jadi jauh lebih nempel. **So isn’t that funny?** (8:05)
 2. Thought on Priorities
 - 1) Akhirnya **overwhelmed**, terus akhirnya bingung sendiri. **So, that’s from me**. (8:06)
 3. Video: How to Communicate Effectively in the Workplace
 - 1) Jadi ceritanya kita mau kenalan sama temen kerja di kantor baru, **let’s start!** (9:50)
- c) Congruent lexicalization

According to Muysken (2000), apart from insertion and alternation, there is a third type of code-mixing. Congruent lexicalization refers to the mixing of words or phrases from languages or dialects that share structural similarities. This form of code mixing occurs morphologically and phonologically.

1. Video: Study Hacks ala Maudy Ayunda

- 1) *Terus kita identifikasi **chapter-chapternya** atau **topic-topicnya**. (3:48)*
- 2) *Dulu biologi I used to that, karena Biologi tuh banyak banget kayak gambar-gambar grafis gitu, dan ada banyak memorization juga karena ada **term-term** tertentu. (7:54)*
2. Video: Thought on Priorities
 - 1) *Buat yang sifatnya kayak gini kita **schedule-in**. (4:45)*
 - 2) *Nah buat aktivitas kayak gini yah mendingan kita **bye-bye** aja. (5:17)*
3. Video: How to communicate effectively in the workplace
 - 1) *Kita pengen bisa ngomong **se-native** mungkin gitu kan. (7:23)*

DISCUSSION OF THE FINDINGS

This research only used two theories proposed by Poplack (1980) and Musyken (2000). There are three types of code-switching used by Maudy Ayunda in this study. They were tag-switching, intra-sentential switching and inter-sentential switching.

The type of Code Switching that Maudy Ayunda often used in her three videos with the theme Maudy's Thought was intra-sentential switching. By switching languages fluently within a single sentence, at the beginning, middle, and end, Maudy Ayunda effectively conveyed her information smoothly and naturally to her viewers. This approach allowed her to maintain flow in her delivery while accommodating both Indonesian and English speakers, enhancing accessibility and engagement with her viewers. This research was supported by Gultom (2021) in his research of the types of code-switching that used by Boy William on Boy William YouTube channel, which showed that the use of intra-sentential switching was more dominant in code-switching in his utterances.

Then, there are three types of code mixing used by Maudy Ayunda in this study. They were insertion, alternation and congruent lexicalization. The type of Code Mixing that Maudy Ayunda often used in her three videos with the theme Maudy's Thought was insertion mixing. Maudy Ayunda frequently used the insertion type more than alternation and congruent

lexicalization in code-mixing because, in her three videos, she frequently inserted English words or phrases into Indonesian sentences to enhance clarity and provide variety in conveying information to her viewers. This research was supported by Virginia & Ambelegin (2021) in their study of the YouTube video "Brown Sugar Battle," which showed that the use of insertion was more dominant in code-mixing. In contrast, Tyra's Titan utterances use few alternations and congruent lexicalization.

With more and more viewers knowing about this type of code-switching and code-mixing, this content provides additional benefits, especially for lay people. By understanding this concept, they can better understand communication in various contexts, opening up new opportunities in understanding social interactions, especially sociolinguistics. As a result, this content not only helps improve learning skills but also broadens one's knowledge of the language.

CONCLUSIONS AND SUGGESTIONS

The analysis showed that a total of 145 data of code-switching and code mixing were found. Maudy Ayunda's most frequently used intra-sentential switching refers to the change of language within a single sentence or clause. There were 57 data of intra-sentential switching. Other types included tag-switching with 5 data, and inter-sentential switching with 20 data. From the 64 data of code-mixing, Maudy Ayunda most frequently used insertion. In addition to focusing on analyzing the types used, the writers suggest that future researchers delve into the factors influencing the use of code-switching and code-mixing. For instance, studies could delve deeper into the social, cultural, and psychological influences on language choice in everyday conversations. Furthermore, exploring the use of other media platforms such as advertisements, magazines, social media, and other media platforms could provide new approaches to sampling and analyzing the variations in code-switching and code-mixing. Thus, future research on code-switching and code-mixing is likely to be more diverse and comprehensive.

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